

IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF REMUNERATION BASED PRISON EMPLOYMENT ON REHABILITATION AND RECIDIVISM: A CASE STUDY OF CENTRAL JAIL, FAISLABAD

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Article History

Received: 05.05.2024

Accepted: 23.05.2024

Published: 01.06.2024

Abstract: This study explores remuneration-based prison employment in the jails of Punjab, Pakistan. The aim is to assess the effectiveness of such employment on the process of prisoner rehabilitation during confinement and upon the rate of recidivism after their release. Using Central jail Faisalabad as a case study this thesis analyses the impact of such a prison employment model on prisoner wellbeing. In the process, it examines the effect that these programs have on the psychological and mental health of the inmates that participate in these labor programs. Data shows that the inmates who are deployed on the remuneration-based prison employment during the confinement are more likely to be rehabilitated and less likely to recidivate after their release as they find some employment on the basis of the skills they acquired during the incarceration. This thesis examines the impact of remuneration-based prison employment on the rehabilitation of inmates. The study utilizes qualitative research methods to evaluate the effectiveness of such programs in improving inmates' employability skills, reducing recidivism rates, and promoting positive behavioral change. The findings suggest that remuneration-based prison employment can have a positive impact on rehabilitation. However, further research is needed to fully understand the underlying mechanisms and to identify best practices for implementation. Overall, the study concludes that remuneration-based prison employment can be a valuable tool in the rehabilitation of inmates, and should be considered as part of a comprehensive rehabilitation strategy.

Keywords: Prisoners, Prison labor, Employment, Rehabilitation, Recidivism.

Cite this article:

Sani, S.A., Abdullah, M.A., Munawar, Z., Javed, Y., (2024). IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF REMUNERATION BASED PRISON EMPLOYMENT ON REHABILITATION AND RECIDIVISM: A CASE STUDY OF CENTRAL JAIL, FAISLABAD. *ISAR Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Studies*, 2(6), 1-7.

1. Introduction

Rehabilitation is a complex phenomenon that involves multiples strategies including skill acquisition and employment during the incarceration and post-release. The process of rehabilitation in jails of Punjab is hampered due to lack of any formal mechanism of Prison employment. The prisoners turn to be bigger criminal and having high rate of recidivism after their confinement in the jails. Criminal Justice System comprises the following organs; Police, Prosecution, Courts, Prisons, Parole and Probation. Being an integral part of Criminal Justice System, Prisons are assigned with the responsibility of detention and correction of offenders and criminals. In the prisons, the convicted inmates are deployed to undergo the prison labor as part of their sentence i.e rigorous imprisonment. However, presently, the prison labor has been transformed more into a tool of offender's rehabilitation than as a mode of punishment. Prison Labor and work programs for convicts who are undergoing their sentences in the prisons are in practice in all over the world, but surprisingly little is known about whether or how these programs contribute to the rehabilitation of offenders during their confinement and after their release. this study assesses the role of prison employment especially remuneration based

employment on the rehabilitation process of inmates. Many international scholars researched to find the evidence of effect based relationship between the treatment being given to inmates during the incarceration and recidivism. As in United States Chen and Sherpao in their article Do harsher prison conditions reduce recidivism? connected the dots between work and lower recidivism¹. Cook, Phillip J, Songman Kang, Anthony A Baraga, Jens Ludwig, and Mallory E O'Brein also worked on the the prisons of US and concluded that work and rehabilitation go hand in hand². Furthermore, Muller smith³ also believed that work has always played a significant role in the correctional experience in American prisons. There are basically two core functions with respect to Prisons ; Security and productivity. The prison administration ensures the security and safety on inmates and engages the on productive activities. The famous and well-documented argument between the creators of the Pennsylvania "solitary" system focused on security only and those of the Auburn "congregate" system encouraging productivity was simply a disagreement over how to organize output in the most productive way possible while maintaining maximum security. In Pakistan, the prisons are mostly security oriented institutions and less

emphasis is given to the productivity and using the inmates as workers. For this purpose, I have tried to establish a broader framework by taking in to loop the prisons work programs all over the world and subsequently to draw a comparison with our prison labor infrastructure. I have consulted the work of Drago, Francesco, Roberto Galbiati, Pitero Vertova⁴, Mastrobuoni and Terlizze⁵ for Italy and that of Bhuller, Manudeep, Gordon B Dahal, Katrine V Loken, and Magne Mostad⁶ for Norway. These authors have taken into account the connection between recidivism and prison employment. Some of them have analyzed the impact of such employment on the process of rehabilitation on inmates inter alia. Whereas, in Pakistan, this segment is highly neglected and lacks some extensive work in the field of prison labor. The objectives of the study are as follows 1. To determine the socioeconomic characteristics of respondents 2. To explore and assess the impact of employment on the rehabilitation process of prisoners during confinement and on recidivism after release. To give some suggestions to the policy makers to improve the correctional facilities. What are the infrastructural and legislative constraints in the optimum utilization of prison labour in commercialized activities? 2. What are the impacts of prison employment on the pace of inmates rehabilitation process and rate of recidivism after the release? 3. What reforms are required for effective Prisons employment including the requisite amendments in Prison Act 1894 and Pakistan prisons rules 1978?

2. Theoretical Support

I have drawn the guidance for this study from the guidelines enumerated in Nelson Mandela Rules 96 and social theory explained by Michele Foucault in his book *Discipline and Punish* (1995). Foucault, explains the power used by social institution as a tool to ensure the discipline. He states that such institutions are in the position to exert their influence upon the behaviors of individuals in society through various means. Many social theorists including Karl Marx, Emile Durkheim, and Thomas Hobbes have talked about and contributed to this theory. Similarly, in the prison setting, the prison administration has a complete control over the space the inmates inhabit. So, the administration deploys the tools, keeping in view their effectiveness, to ensure the discipline among prisoners during the incarceration. Prison employment apparently seems a highly effective tool among them. Secondly, guideline enshrined in Nelson Mandela Rules regarding the Prison work has also been helpful for me, as I assessed the effectiveness of remuneration based prison employment on the rehabilitation on the inmates during the confinement and the recidivism after their release. The theoretical concept that is relevant to my capstone project is the concept of the remuneration in lieu of the Prison employment.

3. Literature Review

For the better comprehension of the imperial framework on the topic of Prisons labor, it is necessary to understand the aim of Prisons labor. The standard minimum rules for treatment of Prisoners prepared by International penal and Penitentiary Commission (1872-1955) elaborates the principles that Prisons labor should a) So far as possible maintain or increase the prisoner's ability to earn an honest living upon release. b) Provide vocational training in useful trades, especially for the young prisoners c) Ensure / facilitate Rehabilitation and low recidivism The logic behind annexing the prison labor with imprisonment is the therapeutic attributes of the work of human life. Ranging from

the psychological impact to the physical wellbeing, it is incumbent upon every individual to undergo the necessary work. The same is the case with the prisons as the inmates have a broader appeal to it. In the modern society, the work is viewed as valuable because it plays the role as a source to identity, status and access to the basics of life. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights by United Nation also acknowledges the work as the basic human right (United Nations, 1948). applying the concept of work on the inmates and freemen, Lippke, elaborates that the quality and nature of work that an individual has access to and performs is a major determining factor of his identity perception by others and by themselves. (Lippke 1998) Hawkins defines the constructive member of a community as a working member. (G. Hawkins 1976) In order to understand the true nature and importance of the Prison labor, it is incumbent upon the researchers to pay attention to the basic concept of labor and its relevance and philosophy to its application to the criminal Justice system. Pertersilia explains that like any other member of society, prisoners also need basic education, training, skill acquisition and employment. The society is supposed to not turn a blind eye to the miseries and plight of inmates. However, if it ignores them, it does not have any right to expect from them for not resuming the life of crimes after their release from the prisons. As the late Chief Justice Warren Burger colorfully and bluntly stated, "We must accept the reality that to confine offenders behind walls without trying to change them is an expensive folly with short term benefits — winning the battles while losing the war. It is wrong. It is expensive. It is stupid." (Petersilia 2003) Prison labor derives its origin from the slavery and servitude's concept of restitution that they are bound to do the labor as a compensation for their misdeeds. The offenders are required to restore the balance of society that was disrupted as a result of their wrong doings against the state or society. In this way, it is not the right of the inmate to perform the prison work but his obligation. Kelesy Timler in her research Paper, "Growing connection beyond Prisons walls" explains the processes of rehabilitation that how a prison garden fosters rehabilitation and healing for incarcerated men. She says that while growing food in prison is beneficial, providing opportunities to donate that food and to nurture connection between growers and recipients has impacts for incarcerated people far beyond the immediate benefits of gardening. These benefits include supporting the self-esteem and self-worth necessary to imagine a future shaped by the experience of giving back through meaningful work. (Timler 2019) Work programs are commonplace in jails and prisons across the country. Both the public and policymakers rate these programs very high. Because of the fact that employment programs reduce the expense of jail for criminals, which in turn benefits taxpayers, governors and legislators view them as sensible economic policy. Inmates who want to escape idleness should be given work, according to prison wardens and the general public. By eliminating inactivity and keeping the offenders busy, the security of the institutions is improved. Work programs support rehabilitation as well. Offenders must cultivate a work ethic in addition to using treatment programs to cope with their addictions, rage, and stupidity (Pierson, et al. n.d.). Many academics disagree on what is detrimental and what is useful to the prisoners participating in these programs when the subject of prison work is discussed. The analysis of these labor programs must take into account a wide range of variables. For instance, in many studies, researchers will examine a certain program from two angles to better understand the difference

between the state run prison labor program and leasing out the labor to private entrepreneurs. These viewpoints are Prison run work programs and private run programs. Following a review of the literature on these labour programs, it is found that the three main topics that are most frequently covered are recidivism and rehabilitation and the prison industrial complex, and the impact that these labour programs have on both the unemployment rate and the country's economy. However, before going into depth of the impacts of prison labour it is essential to understand the philosophy of Prison labor. The idea of labour by inmates and the theory defining its position in criminal justice system must be given careful consideration in order to comprehend the nature of prison industries. On the basis of above discussion, this study formulated the following hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1: Correctional intervention of prison employment is positively associated with the effectiveness of the process of rehabilitation during the incarceration.

Hypothesis 2: Correctional intervention of prison employment is inversely associated with the rate of recidivism after the release

Hypothesis 3: Correctional intervention employment in the prisons is positively associated with relationships of respondents with their family members and friends.

4. Research Methodology

This study examines how the opportunities of remuneration based prison employment leaves the psychological impact upon the inmates that subsequently catalyze the process of rehabilitation. It also examines the comparison regarding rate of recidivism between the inmates who were employed on such programs and who could not avail such opportunity. In this paper, I have used the qualitative method to collect and interpret my data to find out the effectiveness of the remuneration based Prison Employment.

4.1 Data Collection

For the study, data was collected from Industry Branch, Inspectorate of Prisons, Punjab, central Jail Faisalabad and District Jail Sialkot. Furthermore, the data has been obtained from the interviews of 50 prisoners.

4.2 Sampling Technique

In my case study, I have used Randomized Control Trial(RCT) technique of sampling. There are total 2700 inmates confined in central jail, Faisalabad. Out of those 2700, there are 1600 inmates who are convicted prisoners and allowed to undergo prison labor to comply with their sentence of rigorous imprisonment. It is pertinent to mention that the under trial prisoners in jails of Punjab are not allowed to perform any kind of Prison Labor. So the population in my case study was only limited to the convicted prisoners and sample was the selective inmates from two groups i.e who were deployed on remuneration based prison employment and those who were not employed.

4.3 Data Analysis

One of the main components of research is data analysis, which involves analyzing the data gathered using various tools and methodologies for data analysis. In order to get the most appropriate and helpful data for the research to effectively accomplish its objectives, inclusive and exclusive criteria were employed in this study's data analysis. I compared and contrasted the process of rehabilitation between the employed and non-

employed inmates and how they relate to prison labor specifically after gathering all of my data. Additionally, I used these papers to conduct a critical examination of how prison labor affects both the prisoners themselves and the many institutions involved. Along with this analysis, I also looked at the cause-and-effect relationship between inmate rehabilitation and prison employment programs. I utilized Google Drive to categories and code all of the key themes and ideas that I thought were significant within my data and that were most pertinent to my topic in order to arrange my data effectively. I also utilized Google Drive to group all of the downloaded books, articles, and book chapters according to significant themes or ideas. This made it possible for me to swiftly and effectively locate every source I required.

5. Findings

The study was carried out to find out causes of murder among convicted at Borstal Jail Faisalabad, Pakistan to show details about the social, psychological and economic factors.

In this section personal profile of the inmates was studied. An In-depth Interview of 80 convicts detained at Borstal jail Faisalabad was conducted. All the respondents were male below 18 years.

As is shown in Table 2, 95% of the respondents were illiterate while 5% were literate. Out of them, as shown in Table 3, 75% were primary and 25% were middle pass. 85% of the respondents didn't get education due to lack of resources and 15% had no trend of education in their family (Table 4).

Table 2: Education status

Education status	Frequency	Percent
Illiterate	76	95.0
Literate	4	5.0
Total	80	100.0

5.1 Finding 1: Productive day spending

It is irony of the prison system in Punjab that it does have mostly lock-and-key prison instead of open prison available in modern world. In the lock-and-key prison, the prisoners are locked in their rooms for 12 hours and for the remaining 12 hours they are confined in the enclosed premises of jail. Therefore, there is very little leverage for them to utilize their day. Most of the inmates who are deployed on domestic prison labor instead of remuneration based employment perform their domestic duties and spend their leisure time with their fellow inmates. Some of them prefer to spend most of their time in performing the daily religious rituals. (interview 19,20). When the inmates do not have any thing productive to do, they spend their time on watching T.V which is one of the few source of their entertainment (interview 21). An inmate, Amir Sarwar, says that I have no other option but to sit idle the entire day due to lack of an employment (Interview 1). Mr Mustafa Ahmad, Deputy Superintendent Jail, says it is an administrative convenience if the prisoners spend a productive day by getting deployed on some skill-oriented employment (Interview 45) Moreover, an inmate who spends most of his day among criminals, gets such acquaintances which follow them after its release (interview 4,7) Whereas, the inmates who are deployed on the remuneration based prison employment not only go to the factory to acquire the vocational skills but they also perform their production duties and in lieu of them earn the remuneration. They

also spend their rest of the day in productive manners. As Muhammad Arshad, who is earning money inside the prison, explains that he spends his day with discipline and he has set a specific time to perform the daily chores. He starts his day with fajar prayer. He goes to the factory to perform his duties. He cooks food for himself and also plays in the evening (w 11). Azam is excited to learn new things on daily basis (interview 13).

5.2 Finding-2 Psychological Aspect:

After a detailed analysis of the interviews I conducted of two groups one deployed on remuneration based prison employment and second not deployed on remuneration based prison employment there is a great difference regarding their psychological orientation and mental health. The inmates who are not deployed on the productive employment undergo a certain kind of stress and trauma. They are mostly overwhelmed with a sense of guilt and remorse. In order to cope with this mentally traumatic condition, the resort to drugs. As Shahbaz, a prisoner arrested for drugs peddling, says he remains upset as there is a great difficulty in finding the drugs in jail and he remains in search of Drugs (interview 21). Such inmates have to suffer the depression also as Tajamal Ilyas says he remains depressed most of the time due to his parents (interview 19). Most of the inmates of this kind also find themselves getting frustrated due to missing their families and children (interview 20). Regrets and guilt is a dominant factor among these prisoners (interview 20). Most of the Prisoners lost their hopes and leave them at the mercy of the brutal & flawed criminal justice system in Pakistan. As an interviewee says he sees no benefit in placing their hopes on the lawyers. Furthermore, an inmates explained how the financial constraints during his incarceration has turned him into an irritating personality (Interview 8) Whereas on the other hand, the sense of responsibility, self-worth and the awareness of pros and cons of criminal behavior is essential for rehabilitation and mental health (interview 6). The inmates find themselves confident after having acquired the skill and employment. As Arshad writes in his response that he would be having a skill after the release (Interview 11). There is certain level of confidence found in the inmates who are deployed on remuneration based prison employment and they are committed to start a new life after the release (interview 13).

5.3 Finding -3: Effect of employment on rehabilitation:

The major emphasis of this study is to ascertain the impact of remuneration based prison employment on the process of rehabilitation of inmates. Prison labor has long been used as a reformatory tool and remuneration in lieu of prison employment is a step ahead as it relieves the inmates of the sense of guilt and a liability on the family that paves the way of his rehabilitation. Reformation and rehabilitation of the inmates is a subjective concept which cannot be measured but it can be assessed by various factors. One of them is the frequency of the jail offences or discipline breaches during the incarceration.

Furthermore, the behavior and conduct of inmates also reflects the degree of rehabilitation. The prisoners who are not deployed on the remuneration based prison employment are less likely to be rehabilitated as compared to the inmates who are engaged in such employments. As an inmate wishes to learn some skill from jail so that he could do some work inside the prison (Interview 2). Aziz ur Rehman, who has frequent discipline breaches at his discredit, is also of the opinion that the source of earning from the prison can cause a great reduction in negative thinking (interview 4,8).

Whereas, the detailed analysis of the interviews conducted from the inmates who were earning money inside prison clearly reflect that they do not commit the discipline breaches. Furthermore, they also feel rehabilitated. As an interviewees describes that he would not commit crime after release as he has enough opportunity to start a respectable life (interview 11,18).

5.4 Finding-4: Effect of employment on Recidivism:

The ultimate demonstration of the rehabilitation of the inmates is the rate of recidivism. If the inmates are properly reformed in the prisons, there are reintegrated into the society and do not plunge into the crime again. The higher the rate of recidivism, the more flawed the reformatory mechanism of the prisons is. Therefore, the rate of recidivism is also a determining factor to assess the impact of remuneration based prison employment on the inmates. I have drawn a comparison between the inmates who are deployed on remuneration based prison employment and the ones who are not deployed on such employment with respect to the rate of recidivism. Although, Mr. Ibrar Sikandar, could not get the opportunity to earn money during the confinement, yet he is of the opinion that inmates must have the opportunities of employment. It would help them earn their livelihood and become the productive citizens even after the release. Moreover, he fears the indulgence into the crime after the release and attributes it to lack of employment and social factors (Interview-1,5). Similarly, another inmates also dreams of earning money for his family after his release. As he was not given any skills during his confinement, so he intends to be a fruit vendor after his release (interview 2). Similarly, another prisoner having learnt no technical skill has intentions to start the cloth business (interview 3). Abdullah 48 remove this A prisoner finds himself compelled to commit crime for financial gains to cater his family, if he does not find any other source of income (interview 4). In the absence of technical and vocational skills, the availability of financial capital is also required to start up any other business that most of the inmate's lack after their release (interview 6,7). Tajamal Ilyas, who is a repeat offender, complains about the system that he has not found anything new nor he learnt any skill. Although, he pledges not to commit crime, yet he has to plunge into crime again (interview 19). Another inmate, who was not deployed on any employment in his former tenure, still fears to start the drugs peddling again after his release as he has no other way to earn his livelihood (interview 20, 21,23). A rickshaw driver, repeat offender, declares the outer circumstances and sky rocketing inflation responsible for the high crime rate (interview 22,23). The detailed analysis of the repeat offender shows that they did not have any skill and source of income, so they are left with no other option but to commit crime (interview 20 to 28). A prisoner, shahbaz Akhtar, explains that he would not have committed the crime, if he had learnt any skill in his previous tenure (interview 27). According to Zaheer Ahmad Virk, Superintendent Jail, the inmates who are released after getting some vocational skill are less likely to return to the jails in future (Interview 41) Whereas, the inmates who have acquired the skill are confident enough they would not fall prey to poor economic conditions as they find themselves able enough to find a source of earning on the basis of their skill (interview 11,17). Azam says there is no possibility to commit crime after the release as he would establish a tailoring shop and would uplift the economic condition of his family (interview 13,14), another inmate namely Shafiq Shareef intends to establish as laundry shop after the release as he has learnt this skill (Interview 16). The prisoners

who learnt some skill during the confinement were extensively studied and it is a pleasant finding to know that the rate of recidivism among them is zero. My interviews from 29 to 38 are about those inmates who were released after learning some skill and performing Abdullah 49 remove this employment inside prison. They have started up their own set ups for source of income and have not committed crime again (interview 29. Although sometimes they have to put up with difficult circumstances, yet they do not resort to the world of crime (interview 30).

5.5 Finding-5: Insufficiency of the Prison labor infrastructure:

It is an established fact that the present infrastructure is highly insufficient to cater the employment needs of the inmates. Presently, there are approximately 50,000 inmates confined in the jails of Punjab and not more than a hundred are deployed on remuneration-based prison employment. Most of the inmates, I have interviewed are of the opinion that the present infrastructure is not sufficient. (interview 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,9 to 44). However, the Prison department with the collaboration of TEVTA has established multiple training centers and workshops in the jails to impart the skills to the inmates. It offers various courses like electrician, motor winding, motor cycle mechanics, tractor mechanics and tailoring. The same is also appreciated by prisoners but they also complain their insufficiency (interview 3). Aftab Ahmad Bajwa , Superintendent Jail, pointed out that most of the courses offered by TEVTA are meant for convicted inmates who are supposed to stay at the prison for longer term. Either these programs should include the under-trial inmates in their purview or the convicted prisoners should be provided the opportunity of remuneration-based employment (Interview 43). Another interviewee was of the opinion that the entire process of prisoner rehabilitation is flawed and insufficient (interview 12). Furthermore, when the inmates were asked about the suggestions regarding rehabilitation of the inmates, most of them quoted the remuneration-based employment as a tool for the prisoner's reformation. Mian Umair Ikram, Superintendent Jail, recommended the establishment of an infrastructure of remuneration-based employment opportunities for the inmates. He further suggested that it must be executed at the government level (Interview 39). Abdullah 50 remove this Amir Sarwar suggested that there must be a memorandum of understanding between jail administration and the private factories & companies for the better provision of remuneration to the inmates. He furthers highlights the financial prospects for the jail department as well (interview 2,5,10). Aziz-ur-Rehman thinks the jail administration responsible for dispensation of raw material and to protect the financial rights of the prisoners (interview 4). Akhlat Iqbal, Additional Superintendent, highlighted the complications jail administration may face while executing these type of projects as they are likely to jeopardize the security of Prisons (Interview 40). Another prisoner recommends to establish hosiery units, furniture unit and other miscellaneous products like socks etc. the prisons can also initiate the packing services (interview 10)

6. Discussion

Based upon the findings above, it has become evident that the employment can be used as an effective tool for the rehabilitation and reformation of the prisoners. A detailed study of the data obtained from the Prison department and the interviews conducted from the inmates clearly establishes that the present infrastructure

of prison labor/ prison employment is highly insufficient to cater the basic needs of imparting the vocational skills to the prisoners and ensure the provision of respectable remuneration-based prison employment. The basic essence of the prisons is the rehabilitation of the prisoners. It is incumbent upon the prison administration to transform the hardened criminals into the productive citizens of society. The fulfillment of this vision is only possible by some healthy engagement of the prisoners in some productive activity. it is therefore high time to replace the concept of Mushaqat with employment which may also entail some financial incentive as well. This concept of modernizing the prison industry shall lay the foundation for a sound mechanism of the Prisoner rehabilitations. To aid in rehabilitation and reduce recidivism after release was one of the first objectives of these convict labor programs. Numerous programs exist that can successfully achieve this objective. Many prisoners have reported that they have gained a variety of life skills at Central Jail, Faisalabad that will help them once they are released from jail and keep them from returning. These abilities can include hard effort, responsibility, working well with others, and maintaining a positive attitude. These life skills can significantly alter an inmate's perspective and may aid in the rehabilitation process. The correct employment program can be beneficial to an inmate's overall well-being and post-release life, in addition to counselling and vocational training. Prison employment programs that use inmates as laborers and pay them remuneration in lieu of their labor come with a variety of advantages. For instance, offenders receive specialized training and vocational education that will prepare them for employment after they are freed. Some prisoners receive trainings imparted by TEVTA learn how to use and repair tractors, motorcycle, and electric motors which could help them find employment with these equipment once they are freed. Furthermore, the inmates working with various livestock and farm animals, also learn how to tend to crops like lettuce, onions, and broccoli. They will have a lot more success finding and retaining a job following release if they have these new abilities. Prison employment programs not only aid in the rehabilitation of offenders and lower recidivism rates, but they can also improve the bond between a prison and the Prison administration. As the inmates employed on the employment programs are less likely to breach the jail discipline. Furthermore, they can also have the financial prospects for the department. The developed countries have gone to the prison models where the detained inmates are used for such industries which may generate revenue for the department. More or less fifty thousand prisoners are staying idle behind the bars. A handsome amount of revenue can be generated by their engagement into the modern manufacturing. It may also help to improve the exports of the state if the export quality stuff is focused to be manufactured.

7. Conclusion and Future Research

This research has been conducted to explore and assess the impact of remuneration-based employment on the process of rehabilitation of prisoners during the confinement and upon the rate of recidivism after the release from the prison. To do this, I used a case study approach and selected a pilot project of stitching unit established at Central jail, Faisalabad with the help of private entrepreneurs who hired the prison labor on lease basis. They outsource some of the components of textile industry to the inmates who work for them and earn the remuneration in lieu of their labor. I have conducted the interviews deployed on such employment and that of those who are not deployed on such employment. I have also collected the

data from central jail, Faisalabad and Inspectorate of Prisons, Punjab and analyzed the factors of rehabilitation and recidivism on the basis of prison employment. Based upon my findings, it has surfaced that the prison employment in general and remuneration-based prison employment particular has a relationship of direct proportion to the rehabilitation of the inmates during the incarceration and that of inverse proportion to the rate of recidivism after their release from the prison. The inmates deployed on employment have the higher chances of rehabilitation and lower chances of recidivating. Furthermore, these programs can offer offenders vocational training and rehabilitation, cut down on the costs of housing and feeding each inmate, and improve relations between inmates and the administration of prisons in which they reside and work these paras need to be elaborated. Make them at least a page long .

8. Recommendation and Suggestions

The concept of the Mushaqat is no longer applicable in the prison industry. The present day engagement of the prisoners into labor is quite comfortable. Neither it is harsher enough to be called as mushaqat, nor does it qualify the concept of the rigorous imprisonment in the letter and spirit. Today the inmates are learning the technical skills in prisons like any other educational institution and perform their duties in such a conducive and comfortable environment like any other labor-friendly manufacturing unit. The remissions in their sentences are also granted for the engagement of labor. Now it is high time to move a step ahead. The inmates may also be given the monetary incentives which are only possible if some ideas of profit-making manufacturing are implemented. The potentially available suggestions are so viable that they can not only generate revenue for the Prisons Department but the prisoners engaged in that type of productive manufacturing shall also be entitled for the monetary incentives. So the concept of forced labor can be replaced into the incentivized employment.

The already existing prison industry has not evolved with the passage of the time. The manufacturing trades like carpet weaving, iron smiting, carpentry and manual khadian for the handmade fabric were started since the establishment of the prisons. They do still cover the entire prisons industry. The very few new trades have been introduced in the Prisons Industry. The old trades are unviable on two counts; neither have they given the profit making products to earn the revenue, nor these skills help the prisoners to earn their sufficient livelihood after their release from the prisons. These trades have either turned obsolete or they have grown so modernized that the prison's manual industry cannot compete.

The only way to make the prisoner a skilled part of the society is by imparting him the modern day's skills which are applicable today. This is an era of technology and automation. A laborer who has learnt the manual khadi operation of handmade fabric shall not get any employment in the automated textile looms outside after its release. The remedy is the up grading of the prison industry to the level of modern technology manufacturing. It shall not only help sending a lot of technically skilled labor to the society but it shall also help generating the revenue for the department and for the prisoners. For example a carpet of 7 by 4 is woven by 3 weavers and 1 Naqashi in a long span of 3 months. The cost of that carpet in the market is 15000/- RS only. Per day addition of capital by one prisoner is only 40 rupees. Whereas the stitching module suggested in the later part of this report involves 25 labors who make 1500

boxers (underwear) a day. The export price of one boxer is 1.5 dollar. So they are adding the manufacturing 2250 dollars a day. The contribution of every laborer is 90 dollars a day that is 14400/- Rs a day. If the modern day technologies of manufacturing are engaged, they can transform the entire prison management and prison industry. The shall be enough revenue for the department and giving the financial emoluments to the prisoners shall not be a big issue.

The TEVTA centers have been established in all the prisons for this purpose. They are trying to impart the technical skills to the inmates. But the purpose of this project cannot be fully achieved in the absence of the practical implementation. For example, a convicted prisoner sentenced for the life imprisonment is enrolled in the stitching course for two months. He learns the basics of machine and stitching. He is awarded the stitching course certificate. But his unexpired portion of sentence is 15 years. If the skill is useless if not properly practiced during his imprisonment. Whereas if some stitching manufacturing unit on the commercial basis exists in the prisons industry, it shall not only create expertise of laborers but also generate the revenue for all stakeholders. Furthermore, these skills shall be properly utilized during the imprisonment as well.

If the prisons industry intends to join the commercial manufacturing, it shall have to take into account the factors responsible in the open market. The open market can only be competed if the quality and the price of the products are favorable for the buyers. It is very difficult to bring the products in the market after the employment of the conventional methods of the manufacturing. For example, the carpets available in the market are mechanically woven, the wool used is of fine quality and the dyeing colors are of imported quality. The prisoner made carpets shall only be preferred if it is of better quality and cheaper price. So it is suggested to take the necessary measures to compete the market.

To ensure the expertise and specialization of the prisons industry, the technical supervision by the experts is very essential. Mostly the prisons industry is supervised by the administrative officers who do not have enough skills to bring innovation and perfection in the manufactured products. For the technical assistance, the experts should be hired like other manufacturing organizations. For example if a stitching unit is to be established on commercial basis, a supervisor who has enough experience to run the likewise unit be hired from the market.

Qualitative raw material provided to the prison industry is also a big issue. The raw material for the prison industry is provided by the contractor. The quality of the raw material is compromised because of lack of technical expertise of the prison administration. The rates of the raw material are approved by the Inspectorate of Prisons whereas the market rates of the raw material varies . after the deduction of the taxes , the contractor is left most of the time to provide compromised quality of the raw material that jeopardize the quality of the product . Resultantly, the goodwill and reputation of the prisoners made articles are adversely affected. It is requested a proper flexible mechanism of provision of cheaper and quality raw-material be devised for the revival of the Prison industry.

Marketing of the products is as much necessary as the quality and cost of the product. The prisoner made articles have a good enough attention of the customers. A display centre exists adjacent to the camp jail, Lahore. Another display center has been established in

the Art and craft Gallery, Chenab club, Faisalabad and inaugurated by the Chief Minister Punjab. Many of the prisons situating in the hub of the city have the potential to open its own display centers. It is not only important for the commercial transformation of the Prisons industry but it shall also help to portray the progressive image of the prisons Department that it is converting the hardened criminals to the productive elements of society.

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